

Quantum Nature of Gravity to explain Dark Matter and Dark Energy as well as Residual Strong Interaction Force

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- Preprint -

Abstract

Although gravitation as described by Newton is an elementary force, gravity constant G is still the least precisely known in physics. In the 20th century observations on galaxy rotation showed significant violation of Newton's law, leading to ongoing search for Dark Matter (DM) versus modified Newton dynamics. In addition, at the end of the last century observation of accelerated expansion for the Universe raised the issue of missing Dark Energy (DE).

In this article I derive an analytical Elementary Quantum Gravity Model (EQGM) describing quantum nature of gravitation for the Universe and do find qualitative and quantitative agreement with astronomical observations.

It provides a law for zero-point gravitational acceleration explaining observed galaxy rotation. Furthermore, it proves to explain observed DE and DM effects, as well as observed accelerated expansion of the Universe in line with the current Standard Model of Cosmology.

Based on the new model, comprising fluctuations with quantum energy states and quantum exchange particles, discrete gravitational quantum effects between mass objects are proposed. Moreover, a minimum particle mass, granularity of time and entropy for the Universe are derived and discussed.

It is found that gravitation as such can be described out of quantum mechanical uncertainty based on inertia, hence also explaining the corresponding equivalence principle.

Finally, I show that this quantum gravity model extends to also explain the nuclear force, i.e., the residual strong interaction force effect between nucleons in the atomic nucleus.

Key words: quantum gravity, quantum cosmology, dark matter, dark energy, alternative gravity theories, nuclear physics

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I. INTRODUCTION

To date the gravitational force between two mass objects is described by Newton's law [1] as first confirmed in measurement by Henry Cavendish in the 18th century [2]:

$$F_g = \frac{m_1 m_2 G}{r^2}. \quad (1)$$

Since then, it has been tried to describe its nature, leading to general relativity theory of A. Einstein in the 20th century, as a geometric approach on space-time [3]. Although discovered more than three centuries ago, G is still the most imprecisely determined constant in physics [4], with $G = 6.6743 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-2}$ and a relative uncertainty of $2.2 \cdot 10^{-5}$.

Moreover, despite intense and diverse attempts to link gravity and quantum mechanics over the last decades, leading to several competing approaches, none of them proves so far to resolve major inconsistencies qualitatively and quantitatively observed with gravitation in nature. Overviews reflecting the state of research can be found for example in [5], [6], [7].

With advancement in astronomical measurement techniques, it was found from observational statistics of galaxies, that their rotation does not follow the Newton law of gravitation in the outer regime, since forces calculated are too low to explain the higher observed rotational velocities [8]. To solve this issue, at least two directions of research are still followed: The search for DM, to cause an on top gravitational effect in Newton's law, versus modified newton dynamics, which so far is empirical guessing to fit to the observed behavior of galaxies [9].

Even worse, at the end of the 20th century observations led to the conclusion that expansion of the Universe as described by Edwin Hubble is accelerating [10], contradicting the believe that gravitation slows down and would stop its inflation. This leads to search for a missing DE required, being multiples larger than gravitational energy attached to visible matter in the Universe but needs to be in line with observed Standard Model of Cosmology [11].

In this article a model to gain new insights into DM and DE, as well as on the nature of gravitation, is derived.

I follow the approach, that it should be as simple as possible, only as complicated as necessary, and in line with proven observations and physical models.

II. ELEMENTARY QUANTUM GRAVITY MODEL (EQGM)

Following the aim of this article, I use proven quantum mechanical laws and models to compose an Elementary Quantum Gravity Model (EQGM). This means developing an analogue gravity model out of atom and solid-state physics, practically following an idea as proposed for example in [12].

A. Quantum mechanical approach

To introduce quantum mechanics, I start with a one-dimensional Heisenberg uncertainty [13] with $x=r$ to address a radially symmetric Universe and adapt it with the Lorentz factor γ to consider relativistic effects¹. Hence, the variance of momentum and location, as well as of energy and time for a mass object all must have non-zero values. With the reduced Planck quantum of action $\hbar = \frac{h}{2\pi}$ and $h = 6.62607015 \cdot 10^{-34} \text{ J}$ it writes:

$$\sigma_p \sigma_x \geq \frac{\hbar}{2} \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_w \sigma_t \geq \frac{\hbar}{2}. \quad (2)$$

I apply this to a mass object (mo) in the Universe (U). The radius of the Universe is confining the location of the object in a gravitational potential well, while the time uncertainty is related to the time in the Universe.

In the relativistic view, in principle its energy uncertainty can be rooted in its kinetic energy or in its rest energy.

1. Kinetic energy uncertainty

For the first case, using the kinetic energy equivalent for the object from the gravitational potential, the uncertainties are set up as equations, anticipating minimum energy possible:

$$\sqrt{2} \sigma_{wU} = -W_{\text{spot}} = \int_{\infty}^{R_U} \frac{m M_U G}{r^2} dr = \frac{m M_U G}{R_U} = W_{\text{kin}}$$

$$\text{and hence } \sqrt{2} \sigma_{tU} = \frac{2 R_U \hbar}{\gamma m M_U G}. \quad (3)$$

Zero-level for total energy of the mass m is set at infinity. The momentum uncertainty is written up by the mass and velocity uncertainties, with the latter one given by the product of acceleration and time uncertainty:

¹See Appendix A for derivation of a relativistic Heisenberg uncertainty as applied here.

$$\sqrt{2}\sigma_{pU} = \sqrt{2}(\sigma_{mU}\sigma_{aU}\sigma_{tU}) = m_0\gamma a_U t_U, \text{ and} \\ \sqrt{2}\sigma_{xU} = R_U. \quad (4)$$

With this we gain:

$$a_U \geq \frac{M_U G}{2R_U^2}, \quad (5)$$

an inertial acceleration that equals gravitational acceleration due to the equivalence principle, in case of no other forces involved. The Lorentz factor results from the calculated value for σ_{WU} , since kinetic energy shows to have the same value as the rest energy of mass:

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c_0^2}}} = 1 + \frac{\sigma_{WU}}{m_0 c_0^2} = 2. \text{ For the Universe I assume}$$

a radius $R_U = 4.413 \cdot 10^{26} m$, equaling 46.65 billion lightyears and 14,300 Mpc [14], and a mass ² $M_U = 5.943 \cdot 10^{53} kg$.

With this a zero-point acceleration for any mass that cannot be underrun is found:

$$g_{zp} = a_U = 1.018 \cdot 10^{-10} \frac{m}{s^2}. \quad (6)$$

This value is almost identical to what has been empirically found as a_0 at around $1 \dots 1.2 \cdot 10^{-10} m/s^2$, the threshold value to invalidity of Newton's law in galaxy observations [9], [15].

To formulate the EQGM I will use the fundamental Planck-units, as introduced in the year 1899 for basic physical quantities [16]. They are composed only of key constants determining relativistic electrodynamics (speed of light $c_0 = 2.99792458 \cdot 10^8 m/s$), gravitation (gravity constant G), and quantum mechanics (quantum of action h). Furthermore Planck-units describe a limit for quantum effects in gravitation, while Planck-mass can be found in setting the Schwarzschild perimeter of a black hole to be equal to its Compton wavelength [17]: $2\pi r_s = \lambda_C$ with

$$r_s = \frac{m_{pl} G}{c_0^2} \text{ and } \lambda_C = \frac{h}{m_{pl} c_0}, \text{ yielding:}$$

$$m_{pl} = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar c_0}{G}} = 2.178 \cdot 10^{-8} kg. \text{ Moreover Planck-length}$$

defined as: $l_{pl} = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar G}{c_0^3}} = 1.616 \cdot 10^{-35} m$, resulting to

Planck-time for light traveling along it:

$$t_{pl} = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar G}{c_0^5}} = 5.391 \cdot 10^{-44} s, \text{ and the Planck-energy,}$$

exhibiting a value of rest energy for Planck-mass:

$$W_{pl} = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar c_0^5}{G}} = m_{pl} c_0^2 = 1.956 \cdot 10^9 J.$$

With this the Heisenberg uncertainty for mass objects in the Universe can be normalized to Planck-units, while introducing a parameter $\alpha > 0$ as scale factor:

$$(m_{pl} \alpha \gamma) \sigma_a \left(\frac{t_{pl}}{\alpha} \right) \sigma_x \geq \frac{\hbar}{2}. \quad (7)$$

From this the same value for the zero-point acceleration as already calculated above does result:

$$a_U \geq \frac{c_0^2}{2R_U} = 1.018 \cdot 10^{-10} \frac{m}{s^2}. \quad (8)$$

Comparing with Eq. (5), it is found:

$$G = \frac{R_U c_0^2}{M_U}. \quad (9)$$

The perspective is, that gravity ‘‘constant’’ appears as a parameter. With this and Eq. (3) the minimum kinetic energy for a mass in the Universe results to:

$$W_{kin} = m c_0^2. \quad (10)$$

This result is also found from the uncertainty relations. Although this is the same value as for the rest energy of mass, it is a kinetic energy appearing on top, since being linked to momentum in the uncertainty relations:

$$\sqrt{2}\sigma_{WU} = m_{mo} \gamma \sqrt{2}\sigma_a R_U = m c_0^2 = W_{kin}. \quad (11)$$

2. Rest energy uncertainty

For the second case that rest energy fluctuations would make up energy uncertainty, the results are the same as in the section given above, since kinetic and rest energy have been found to exhibit identical values. The difference in derivation required is that σ_m is the fluctuating uncertainty with the effective average being equal to mass observed, that thus would have no fixed value over time. Consequently, acceleration σ_a must be replaced by the

² As part of the problem with DM and DE, the value for the mass of the Universe cannot be exactly known a priori. An explanation for why I can assume the mass of the Universe as stated here is given in section III.C..

fixed value of g_{zp} instead:

$$\sqrt{2}\sigma_{WU} = \sqrt{2}\sigma_{mmo}\gamma g_{zp} R_U = mc_0^2 = W_{kin}. \quad (12)$$

B. Gravitational energy potential of the Universe

The model for gravitational energy potential for a mass in the Universe consists of two regimes: Outside for $R > R_U$ in the vacuum it is hyperbolic, as given in Eq. (3).

Inside for $R \leq R_U$ one can assume a homogeneous mass density which is for a mass in intergalactic space, distant from any singularity and thus facing a parabolic potential:

$$W_{gUi} = \int_{R_U}^R \frac{mM_U G(r/R_U)^3}{r^2} dr = \frac{mc_0^2}{2} \left[\left(\frac{R}{R_U} \right)^2 - 1 \right]. \quad (13)$$

Thus, the kinetic energy gained from the mass within the homogeneous Universe is $(1/2)mc_0^2$ at maximum on top of the zero-point energy. Figure 1 shows the combined gravitational potential for a Planck-mass.

FIG. 1. The potential of gravitational energy W_{gpot} [J] for an object with Planck-mass in a homogeneous Universe depending on its radial position r [m]. The zero-point energy level at $r = R_U$ is indicated by the dotted-dashed line.

In case of inhomogeneous mass distribution, including singularities, the kinetic energy of a mass within the Universe will increase beyond the factor $3/2$ of the value of its rest energy³.

C. Quantization of gravitation

To describe gravitational quantization for a mass object, this needs also to be done for two cases: First for the hyperbolic potential describing inhomogeneous mass

densities and singularities, and second for parabolic potentials describing homogeneous mass densities.

3. Inhomogeneous mass density constellations

To describe interaction between two mass objects I use an analogy to proven laws from atom and solid-state physics, namely the quantum model for an electron in the Coulomb potential of a hydrogen atom. This has been found by N. Bohr more than a century ago and explains the stability of atoms due to finite and quantized energy levels arising, despite a hyperbolic singularity potential [18]. Bohr's postulate:

$$pr \equiv \hbar n, \text{ with: } n \in \mathbb{N}, \quad (14)$$

is a discretized Heisenberg uncertainty, equaling integer multiples of Planck's quantum of action with the product of momentum and location.

(a) Non-relativistic case

With this, quantized energies and radii were obtained for the electron in the hydrogen atom:

$$W_{qC} = \frac{-q^2}{8\pi\epsilon_0 r_B n^2} \text{ and Bohr radius: } r_B = \frac{4\pi\epsilon_0 \hbar^2}{m_e q^2}. \quad (15)$$

I transfer this to a model for gravitation between mass objects. Since Coulomb and gravitation force laws are similar related to the formula above, except for a factor $G/(8\pi\epsilon_0)$ and charge q^2 to be replaced by the product of mass m and M , we gain:

$$W_{qgpot} = \frac{-mMG}{r_{gB} n^2} = \frac{-m^3 M^2 G^2}{\hbar^2 n^2} = -W_{kin}, \quad (16)$$

and a "gravitational Bohr radius":

$$r_{gB} = \frac{\hbar^2}{m^2 MG} = \frac{\lambda_c^2}{R_U} \frac{M_U}{M}. \quad (17)$$

With $\lambda_c = \frac{\hbar}{mc_0}$ being the reduced Compton wavelength

for a mass object m , meaning that its rest energy equals the energy of a photon with this wavelength. This is known as minimum size for which a reasonable radius of the mass object m can be defined due to quantum uncertainty.

In the three-dimensional spherical Bohr atom model, each energy state n can be occupied with a maximum of $2n^2$

³ From the perspective within the Universe these energies cannot be perceived directly for mass objects in proximity, since they are experiencing the same gravitational and inflationary accelerations, being equal to inertial acceleration due to the equivalence principle.

fermionic mass objects, hence resulting to a total number of quantum states available of $2n^3$. Hence N mass objects confined in a sphere with radius R will occupy the states up to the highest kinetic energy known as the Fermi energy [19] adding on top of the zero-point energy level:

$$W_F = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left(\frac{3\pi^2 N}{(4/3)\pi R^3} \right)^{\frac{2}{3}}. \quad (18)$$

(b) Relativistic case

A relativistic Bohr postulate with the Lorentz factor to consider increase of inertia in the inertial system of the Universe (U) and contraction of length in the inertial system of the mass object (mo) on the circular trajectory to meet the quantization criteria is set up:

$$p_U r_{mo} = m\gamma v_U r_U \gamma^{-1} \equiv \hbar n. \quad (19)$$

For the velocity of the mass object, it is gained from the formula for relativistic kinetic energy:

$$W_{kin} = (\gamma - 1)mc_0^2, \text{ thus}$$

$$v_U = c_0 \sqrt{1 - \frac{1}{(1 + \beta)^2}}, \text{ with: } \beta = \frac{W_{kin}}{mc_0^2}. \quad (20)$$

After simplification for $\beta \gg 1$ this yields for the relativistic gravitational Bohr radius to be the reduced Compton wavelength of the mass object m within the inertial system of the Universe and for the kinetic energy⁴ of mass:

$$r_{gB} = \frac{\hbar}{mc_0} = \overline{\lambda}_C \text{ and } W_{kin} = \frac{m^2 M G c_0}{n\hbar}. \quad (21)$$

Reformulating, I find an expression that can be interpreted as containing a quantum exchange particle I call ‘‘Ghton’’ (Gh)⁵ in analogy to a Photon since it seems to be moving with the speed of light:

$$W_{kin} = \frac{(mc_0^2)^2}{n_{Gr} W_{Gh}} = W_{Gr}(n_{Gr}), \text{ with:}$$

⁴Out of this, relativistic effects $W_{kin} > mc_0^2$ apply, if $(mM) > m_{pl}^2$. For the case that the mass object is at $r=R_U$, i.e. $\beta=1$, it is:

$$r_{gB} = \frac{2\hbar}{\sqrt{3}mc_0}, \text{ and for the kinetic energy: } W_{kin} = \frac{\sqrt{3}m^2 M G c_0}{2n\hbar}.$$

⁵ The Ghton for the Universe can also be found for the non-relativistic case in reformulating Eq. (16) above:

$$-W_{\text{grav}} = \frac{mMG}{r_{gB} n^2} = \frac{m^3 M^2 G^2}{\hbar^2 n^2} = \frac{(mc_0^2)^3}{n_{Gr}^2 W_{Gh}^2} = W_{kin} = W_{Gr}(n_{Gr}).$$

$$W_{Gh} = \frac{\hbar c_0}{R_U} = 7.17110^{-53} J. \quad (22)$$

For the quantized energy state levels, I call these quasi-particles ‘‘Gravons’’ (Gr), with n_{Gr} the Graviton quantum number. This is in analogy to the Phonon, the quasi-particle for the energy states of collective atom oscillations in solid-state crystals [19].

The corresponding de Broglie wavelength of the Ghton is $\lambda_{Gh} = 2\pi R_U = 2.77 \cdot 10^{27} m$ with a frequency of $f_{Gh} = 1.081 \cdot 10^{-19} Hz$, thus can be thought of as spanning along the perimeter of the Universe. For the matter waves associated to the relativistic Gravons it can be written:

$$\lambda_{Gr} = \frac{\hbar c_0}{W_{kin}} = \frac{2\pi r_{gB} n_{Gr} W_{Gh}}{W_0}, \text{ with } W_0 = mc_0^2. \quad (23)$$

For example, for a Planck-mass at the boarder of the Universe we can calculate while setting $r_{gB} := R_U$:

$$n_{Gr}(m_{pl}, R_U) = \frac{R_U m_{pl} c_0}{\hbar} = 2.73110^{61}. \quad (24)$$

Consequently, for a higher number of smaller mass objects, there must be a limit, thus otherwise these would have to occupy states also outside the Universe in the hyperbolic continuum – like what is known from the Chandrasekhar limit for white dwarf stars [20]. In contrary, for larger mass objects the available quantum states will only be merely filled-up. In the relativistic case the Fermi energy adding on top of the zero-point energy level is based on the relativistic momentum and de Broglie wavelength, with N the number of mass objects:

$$W_F = \hbar \pi c_0 \left(\frac{3N}{(4/3)\pi^2 R^3} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} = W_{Gh} \left(\frac{9\pi N}{4} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}}. \quad (25)$$

From Eq. (21), also a minimum for the mass required for an object to exist in the current Universe can be interpreted:

$$m_{minU} = \frac{\hbar}{R_U c_0} = \frac{W_{Gh}}{c_0^2} = 7.970 \cdot 10^{-70} kg. \quad (26)$$

Finally, a minimum for the size of the Universe from current perspective could be hypothesized, if ground state $n_{Gr}=1$ with Ghotons acting between two halves of the mass of current Universe is assumed⁶:

$$R_{U00} = \frac{\hbar}{4M_U c_0} = 1.480 \cdot 10^{-97} m. \quad (27)$$

4. Homogeneous mass density constellations

For a Universe with homogeneous mass density, the mass objects are confined in the parabolic potential according to Fig. 1, and the relativistic case does apply:

$$W_{kin}(n_{Gr}) = mc_0^2 \left[\frac{3}{2} - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{r(n_{Gr})}{R_U} \right)^2 \right], \text{ with:} \quad (28)$$

$$r(n_{Gr}) = n_{Gr} r_{gB} = n_{Gr} \frac{\hbar}{mc_0}.$$

This can be reformulated to:

$$W_{kin}(n_{Gr}) = W_0 \left[\frac{3}{2} - \frac{1}{2} n_{Gr}^2 \left(\frac{W_{Gh}}{W_0} \right)^2 \right]. \quad (29)$$

Consistently with Eq. (24), for a Planck-mass at zero-point the same quantum number it is found:

$$n_{Grzp}(m_{Pl}, R_U) = \frac{R_U}{r_{gB}} = \frac{m_{Pl} c_0^2}{W_{Gh}} = 2.731 \cdot 10^{61}, \text{ and}$$

$$W_{kin}(m_{Pl}, n_{Grzp}) = W_{zp}(m_{Pl}) = m_{Pl} c_0^2. \quad (30)$$

To the relativistic Graviton energies, matter wavelengths and related frequencies in the range of $10^{-34} m$ and $10^{42} Hz$ do result, respectively:

$$\lambda_{Gr}(m, n_{Gr}) = \frac{hc_0}{W_{kin}(n_{Gr})} = \frac{2\pi r_{gB}}{\frac{3}{2} - \frac{1}{2} n_{Gr}^2 \left(\frac{W_{Gh}}{W_0} \right)^2}. \quad (31)$$

5. Quantum state occupation and particles in the Universe

To determine quantum state occupation and degree of degeneracy⁷ indicated by Fermi energy as compared to the

depth of the homogeneous Universe parabolic quantum well, the size of the smallest elementary mass particle(s) and their volume(s) in the Universe must be known as well. As can be seen for the artificial case of a Universe with Planck-mass as elementary particles, these would be far from degeneracy:

$$W_{FPl} = 4.140 \cdot 10^{-32} J, \text{ versus:}$$

$$W_{potU} = \frac{1}{2} m_{Pl} c_0^2 = 9.78 \cdot 10^8 J, \text{ with:}$$

$$N_{Pl} = \frac{M_U}{m_{Pl}} = 2.731 \cdot 10^{61}.$$

An elementary mass particle would have to fill all available quantum states in the Universe to cause degenerate matter pressure and thus drive expansion of the Universe, as initially described in [21].

With baryonic mass observed [11] and Eq. (25) one can calculate mass and volume of such particle (X) required if it would have to make up missing DM with $\Omega_{DM} = \Omega_M - \Omega_b = 0.315 - 0.049 = 0.266$.

$W_{FX} := \frac{1}{2} m_X c_0^2$ would be required, yielding:

$$m_X = \left(\frac{2\hbar\pi}{c_0} \right)^{\frac{3}{4}} \left(\frac{9}{4} M_U \frac{\Omega_{DM} / \Omega_b}{\pi^2 R_U^3} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}}.$$

This delivers $m_X = 1.743 \cdot 10^{-38} kg$ and

$$N_X = \frac{M_U \Omega_{DM} / \Omega_b}{m_X} = 1.851 \cdot 10^{92}. \quad \text{Thus, the}$$

corresponding rest energy, average kinetic energy and black body radiation temperature of the particle would be:

$$W_X = m_X c_0^2 = 9.780 meV, \quad W_{kinm} = \frac{3}{5} W_{FX} = 2.934 meV,$$

and $T_X = 12.067 K$. A candidate for this is the Neutrino with yet unknown, but smallest mass of all elementary particles in the Universe known so far. It is assumed to have the highest particle density in the Universe. However, since its temperature in the observed Cosmic Neutrino Background (CNB) is only $1.945 K$ [11] and its appearance is assumed "only" a billion times higher ($n_n = 340 cm^{-3}$, $N_n = 1.221 \cdot 10^{89}$) than the number of nucleons in the Universe, it can contribute less than one percentage point to missing DM.

To conclude, to date no elementary particle could be

⁶ If at minimum size the Universe is determined by degeneration in quantum statistics of mass objects this becomes invalid.

⁷ An alternative formulation for degeneracy is that mass object distance be smaller than the corresponding de Broglie wavelength of the mass object, which is far from being the case for nucleons in the current Universe and any mass larger than this.

identified as a candidate to explain extra mass required as DM.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Since mass objects do mostly differ, in the EQGM this offsets the minimum energy level for each value of mass as can be seen from Eq. (28) for the Graviton energy above. Moreover, the Universe appears only homogeneous at scale, but is made of clusters of galaxies, solar systems, stars, planets, dust, gas, etc. as local structures, all of them representing gravitational potential wells.

This leads to coupled potentials of different size. Superposition of quantum states can be assumed to lead to split-up of energy states into quasi-continuums for objects being in proximity, as this is well-known for electrons in the coulomb potentials within solid-state crystals. Concluding, we can assume that every mass object is finding an unoccupied energy state in the current Universe.

Quantization effects in the motion of mass objects may become obvious under some circumstances - as for example with the zero-point acceleration in intergalactic space at the outer range of galaxies - but not be perceived due to tiny Ghoton energies between Gravitons and/or continuum effects in most other cases.

Note that the EQGM derived above does not require the existence of a space beyond the radius of the Universe. This is also since I have described it based on a quantum mechanical potential well perspective from within the Universe.

A. Explanation for Dark Matter effect and quantum gravitation law

At a galaxy Newton gravitational acceleration is imposed on any mass object with: $g_N(r) = \frac{M_{Gx}G}{r^2}$. (32)

According to the EQGM described in this work, a gravitational zero-point quantum fluctuation acceleration in the Universe would need to take effect as well.

Looking into the modified Newton dynamics (MOND) approach, which is empirically fitted to observations [9], the MOND fit models [15] are:

$$g_{MOND}(r) = \frac{M_{Gx}G}{\mu\left(\frac{g_{MOND}(r)}{a_0}\right)r^2} \text{ with estimated}$$

$a_0 = 1.110^{-10} m/s^2$ and the fit functions are defined as:

$$\mu_1(x) = \frac{x}{1+x} \text{ and alternatively: } \mu_2(x) = \frac{x}{\sqrt{(1+x^2)}}.$$

Out of this, it is gained with μ_1 :

$$g_{MOND1}(r) = \frac{M_{Gx}G + \sqrt{M_{Gx}^2G^2 + 4r^2a_0M_{Gx}G}}{2r^2},$$

while applying μ_2 yields:

$$g_{MOND2}(r) = \sqrt{\frac{M_{Gx}^2G^2 + \sqrt{M_{Gx}^4G^4 + 4r^4a_0^2M_{Gx}^2G^2}}{2r^4}}.$$

Meaning that for $g_{MOND}(r) \gg a_0$ the gravitational acceleration equals the Newton law, while for $g_{MOND}(r) \ll a_0$, i.e. with large values for r, it behaves like:

$$g_{MOND}(r) \rightarrow \frac{\sqrt{a_0M_{Gx}G}}{r}. \quad (33)$$

In the following I want to gain some insights into the effects behind the MOND using the EQGM.

It was found with Eq. (8) above, that the value for the zero-point gravitational quantum fluctuation acceleration of a mass object in the Universe a_U appears to be identical to the MOND fit parameter a_0 . From this, I can rewrite Eq. (33) so that $g_{MOND}(r) \rightarrow \sqrt{a_U} g_N(r)$ results in the deep-MOND regime, i.e. for large values of r it delivers the geometric mean of the Newtonian acceleration and the zero-point quantum fluctuation acceleration for a mass object in the Universe.

Since both acceleration vectors can be seen as stochastic quantum variables described by variances - see section I. below - the overall acceleration can be understood as a covariance of quantum uncertainty accelerations:

$Cov(\vec{a}_U, \vec{g}_N(r)) = \vec{a}_U \vec{g}_N(r)$. We find a special case here,

with covariance simply equaling the product of both stochastic variables. This means the vectors are correlated; hence the scalar product is at its maximum, meaning they do exhibit identical direction for the accelerations⁸. This also leads to the Heisenberg uncertainty inequation as in Eq. (11) becoming an equation, i.e. following the principle of minimum energy required by acceleration uncertainty

⁸ The covariance for two stochastic variables is defined as: $Cov(X, Y) = \sigma_x \sigma_y = E(XY) - E(X)E(Y)$. Here, with the expectation value

being the sum of parallel vectors for $\vec{g}_N(r)$ and \vec{a}_U .

To analyze this, I do derive a perturbation approach for a mass object in the internal gravitation field of a galaxy. In this the zero-point quantum fluctuation acceleration in the Universe is acting on the location of the mass object as an on-top external field as:

$$\Delta g_{zp}(r) = M_{Gx} G \left[\frac{1}{(r - \Delta r_g)^2} - \frac{1}{(r + \Delta r_g)^2} \right] \cong \frac{4M_{Gx} G a_U}{c_0^2 r}$$

, or with using Eq. (8) and Eq. (9):

$$\Delta g_{zp}(r) = \frac{2M_{Gx} c_0^2}{M_U (1 - (r/R_U)^2)^2 r} \cong \frac{2M_{Gx} c_0^2}{M_U r^2},$$

with the approximations on the right-hand sides being valid, if the distance r is by at least an order of magnitude smaller than the radius of the Universe.

The effective location-induced acceleration perturbation is

written as: $\Delta r_g = \frac{1}{4} a_U \tau_g^2 = \frac{r^2}{R_U}$, with the propagation

time for the gravitational effect between the mass center of the galaxy and the mass object to emerge: $\tau_g = \frac{2r}{c_0}$.

Note that despite the location symmetry of the quantum fluctuation, due to the non-linearity of the Newtonian gravitation this perturbative acceleration is non-zero and directed towards the mass center of the galaxy, i.e. being parallel to the Newtonian vector.

Another conclusive feature in this model is, that a mass object could never leave the Universe, since r approaching R_U would lead to an infinite acceleration holding it back.

Based on the MOND empirical model, the gravitation caused by the external field effect (EFE) [15] in the case that $a_{int} < a_{ext} < a_0 \equiv a_U$ can be calculated from the quantum fluctuation perturbation of the Newtonian set up above including a scale-up factor γ_{EFE} , hence yielding:

$$\Delta g_{zpEFE}(r) = \gamma_{EFE} \Delta g_{zp}(r) = \sqrt{a_U g_N(r)}, \text{ since:}$$

$$\gamma_{EFE} = \frac{a_0}{\Delta g_{zp}(r_0)} = \frac{c_0^2}{4\sqrt{M_{Gx} G a_U}}, \text{ and while the boarder-}$$

line radius where Newtonian gravitation is equal to the MOND acceleration fit parameter interpreted as the zero-

point quantum fluctuation acceleration is: $r_0 = \sqrt{\frac{M_{Gx} G}{a_U}}$.

Hence the total gravitational acceleration is:

$$g_{EQGM}(r) = g_N(r) + \Delta g_{zpEFE}(r). \quad (34)$$

Below, Fig. 2a (linear scale) and Fig. 2b (double logarithmic scale) exhibit comparisons between the Newtonian, the empirical MOND models, and the EQGM model, demonstrating the congruence between the empirical MOND and the analytical EQGM model, while EQGM delivers slightly higher accelerations.

FIG. 2a. Comparison of gravitational acceleration g [m/s²] depending on center distance r [m] at a typical galaxy calculated from Newton's law (circles), the MOND1 (squares) and MOND2 (rhombs) formulas and based on quantum zero-point acceleration law from EQGM (crosses), respectively. Furthermore, a_0 MOND fit parameter is shown (dashed line).

In case of more complex settings like for a mass object in the range of several galaxies, like in a galaxy cluster, the simple deep-MOND formula cannot be applied. Moreover, the total gravitation effect on the mass object must be calculated from vectors with different directions and dependencies on $(1/r)$ versus $(1/r^2)$, which is left for further study.

To summarize, the EQGM approach from this work provides an analytical explanation for the empirical observations and MOND models on galaxy behavior. A DM assumption to explain additional gravitational

$E(a_U) = 0$ due to quantum fluctuation, only the expectation value for the product of the two stochastic variables is non-zero.

acceleration in the outer regimes of galaxies is not required here due to zero-point quantum fluctuation acceleration acting on all mass objects being confined in the Universe.

FIG. 2b. Acceleration functions as shown and already described in FIG. 2a above but displayed in double logarithmic scale.

B. Explanation for Dark Energy and accelerated expansion of the Universe

The zero-point energy described above causes a repulsive (i.e. expansive) pressure in the Universe as contained in an outside vacuum, while acting against the attracting gravitational forces. Accordingly, this energy is a candidate to explain DE.

At the border of the universe at $r=R_U$ the pressure is made up by the kinetic zero-point energy of the mass object fluid in the Universe itself. The DE is appearing in the Universe as the kinetic expansion energy of masses as perceived by any observer witnessing Hubble inflation. The radial expansive pressure is:

$$P_{exp} = \frac{-W_{zpU}}{(4/3)\pi R_U^3} = \frac{-M_U c_0^2}{(4/3)\pi R_U^3} = -\rho_U c_0^2. \quad (35)$$

The gravitational, deflationary pressure calculated according to the hydrostatic approach is:

$$P_{gU}(R_U) = \int_0^{R_U} \rho(r) g_U(r) dr = \frac{1}{2} \rho_U c_0^2. \quad (36)$$

Hence an effective pressure of:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta P &= P_{exp} + P_{gU} = P_{exp} + P_{gN} + P_{gzp} \\ &= -\frac{1}{2} \rho_U c_0^2 = -0.742 \cdot 10^{-10} \frac{N}{m^2} \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

acting like a net „negative gravitation“, and an acceleration for the scale parameter a do result at the boarder of the Universe:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta g &= \frac{\Delta P \cdot 4\pi R_U^2}{M_U} = \frac{-3c_0^2}{2R_U} = -3g_{zp} = -3.055 \cdot 10^{-10} \frac{m}{s^2}, \text{ and} \\ \ddot{a} &= \frac{-\Delta g}{R_U} = 6.921 \cdot 10^{-37} s^{-2}. \end{aligned} \quad (38)$$

Related to the notation used in the current Standard Model of Cosmology (Λ -CDM model) with w being the DE factor in the equation of state, this results to $w = -1$ in line with observations from [10] and with ESA Planck results [11], as well as with WMAP results [14].

From the EQGM - considering classical Newton and on top zero-point gravitational acceleration - the DE density is $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.666$, two-fold the gravitational energy density attached to the mass of the Universe at $\Omega_M = 0.333$, if energy densities from radiation Ω_r and curvature of space Ω_K can be neglected.

ESA Planck results from Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) analysis exhibit $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.685$ and $\Omega_M = 0.315 (+/-0.007)$, if Ω_K is set to zero. With the extended Λ -CDM model, Ω_K is found around $0.025 (+/-0.02)$ [11], with this EQGM results being in line for Ω_M and Ω_Λ .

For the case that energy densities were analyzed based on observations of galaxy lensing, i.e. with underlying gravitation effects also beyond the zero point gravitational acceleration, ESA Planck [11] and WMAP results [14] are found in the regimes around $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.73$ and $\Omega_M = 0.27$. This points to a case where zero-point gravitational acceleration partial pressure

$$P_{gzp} = g_{zp} \frac{M_U}{4\pi R_U^2} = \frac{c_0^2}{2R_U} \frac{M_U}{4\pi R_U^2} = \frac{\rho_U}{6} c_0^2 \text{ might have to}$$

be skipped in calculation of ΔP above, since not dominating the observation. This would lead to a ratio of 3:1 for Ω_Λ (75%): Ω_M (25%) from EQGM.

But this needs further study, as well as the general systematic observational tension found in Hubble constant obtained from CMB versus from galaxy populations – see comprehensive review and discussion in [22].

However, latest results from Dark-Energy Survey (DES) [23] do even result to $\Omega_M = 0.339 (+/-0.03)$, $w = -1$, very well in line with the holistic approach on the Universe described by EQGM.

To conclude, the EQGM can also provide an explanation for DE, while relative precision based on currently available observations is in the range of $+/- 0.03$ for the energy densities. According to EQGM the total on top energy appearing in the Universe is:

$$W_{Uzp} = M_U c_0^2 = DE = DM c_0^2 = 5.341 10^{70} J . \quad (39)$$

Thus, the equivalent mass associated with this DE is the mass of the Universe M_U itself, which is also acting as DM.

C. Implications on and from the Gravity constant

Comparing the two different expressions derived above for the zero-point acceleration a_U , an analytical formula

for the gravity constant was found: $G = \frac{R_U c_0^2}{M_U}$. Thus

gravity “constant” appears as a parameter, depending on radius and mass of the Universe. At least there is no requirement for the more exceptional case that it be a fundamental constant of nature. Hence G will change over time in a non-stationary Universe if the ratio R_U / M_U is not constant. This would feedback on its evolution, leading to non-linear effects. However, regardless of how R_U and M_U evolve, they cancel out in the calculation for the kinetic zero-point energy⁹ of a mass in the Universe, that thus will always be identical to the value of its rest energy.

Due to the problem of DM and DE the exact value of mass M_U was unknown so far. However, since I found the formula above which is confirmed by the identity of calculated and observed zero-point acceleration, the mass M_U can be calculated out of it if a value for radius R_U is given.

To what extend would mankind have been able to observe a change in G over the course of research, i.e., time T_{Go} from years 1798 to 2023? The answer is: Not at all, assuming a change of its radius based on the Hubble expansion [11] of:

$$\Delta G = H_0 T_{Go} = 1.551 10^{-8} ,$$

with $H_0 = 67.4 \frac{km/s}{Mpc} = 2.184 10^{-18} s^{-1}$, since

impreciseness of measured values for G being three orders of magnitude larger [4].

The formula for G is also the event horizon of a stationary

finite low density black hole. However, which is different from a dark star black hole that would exhibit a Schwarzschild radius r_s as its event horizon, which is double the value of r_{bh} [24]. Hence mass of the Universe M_U also might be increased from outside of it. Looking at the critical mass density required to form a black hole, the Universe is below this regarding its average density:

$$\rho_U = \frac{M_U}{(4/3)\pi R_U^3} = 1.650 10^{-27} kgm^{-3} , \text{ versus:}$$

$$\rho_{Cr} = \frac{3H_0^2}{8\pi G} = 8.533 10^{-27} kgm^{-3} .$$

D. Gravitational zero-point fluctuations

With the EQGM derived above, zero-point kinetic energy of a mass in the Universe has a value equal to its rest energy but appearing on top. It can be understood in a classical manner as gravitational self-energy rooted in the potential of the Universe, and in a quantum mechanical view as being required from the Heisenberg uncertainty due to confinement in its potential. However, how can this relatively high on top energy and the attached zero-point acceleration for mass objects be understood and why is it not observed directly? Key to understand is the quite short Planck-time scale t_{pl} / α in which uncertainty is taking place. In case of absence of other forces, we can also calculate the fluctuation kinetic energy W_{fluc} and a zero-point fluctuation distance r_{fluc} that is caused for the non-localized mass, with $\sqrt{2}\sigma_{xU} = R_U$, while probability distribution is spread across the Universe:

$$W_{fluc} = \frac{1}{2} m \left(g_{zp} \frac{t_{pl}}{\alpha} \right)^2 , \text{ and } r_{fluc} = \frac{1}{2} g_{zp} \left(\frac{t_{pl}}{\alpha} \right)^2 . \quad (40)$$

With using Eq. (5), (6), (8), this can be written as:

$$W_{fluc}(m) = \frac{\hbar m_{pl}^2 c_0}{8mR_U M_U} = \frac{W_{Gh} m_{pl}^2}{8 m M_U} = m c_0^2 \frac{r_{fluczp}}{2R_U} , \text{ yielding:}$$

$$W_{fluc}(m_{pl}) = 3.279 10^{-115} J . \quad (41)$$

$$r_{fluc}(m) = \frac{\hbar m_{pl}^2}{4M_U c_0 m^2} = \frac{r_{gBr} m_{pl}^2}{4 m M_U} , \text{ yielding:}$$

$$r_{fluc}(m_{pl}) = 1.480 10^{-97} m . \quad (42)$$

demonstrating that this fluctuation energy is too tiny to be observed directly. However, energy density of the fluctuations in the spherical shell with thickness $r_{fluc} / 3$ is

⁹Based on Eq. (3) while inserting the formula for G from Eq. (9), and confirmed by Eq. (11) not depending on G.

identical as for the zero-point energy of the mass object related to the entire Universe:

$$w_{fluc} = \frac{W_{fluc}}{4\pi R_U^2 (r_{fluc} / 3)} = \frac{mc_0^2}{(4/3)\pi R_U^3} = w_{zp}. \quad (43)$$

E. Gravitational quantum particles and matter waves

First gravitational particles were assumed by Pierre-Simon Laplace more than two centuries ago, while a quantum mechanical particle named Graviton was mentioned around the mid-20th century. In the diverse set of quantum gravity approaches the Graviton is mostly, but not always, assumed to be the exchange quantum of gravitation. However, also further particles were proposed, like Gravitino, Goldstino, Sgoldstino, Gravissskalar and Gravivektor [25].

In the EQGM each mass object has a quantized gravitational energy state – dubbed with the quasi-particle name “Gravon” – and a de Broglie matter wave [26] associated. The gravitational effect is assumed to be realized via the quantum exchange particle dubbed Ghoton, moving at the speed of light. For a mass object to change its gravitational energy, i.e. Gravon state, Ghotons have to be emitted to decrease, or absorbed to increase its gravitational energy, respectively.

Both, Ghoton and Gravon, quantum particle energies are inversely proportional to the confinement space, i.e. the distance between interacting mass objects. In case of interaction considered between a mass and the entire mass of the Universe this is the radius of the Universe R_U .

Regarding gravitational coupling significant effects must be expected due to relativistic kinetic zero-point energy of mass in the Universe. For derivation of a quantum gravitational coupling parameter see Appendix C.

To conclude, in the EQGM the Ghoton is the exchange particle to play the role of the Graviton, while the Gravon is a quasi-particle representing the matter waves associated with DE and DM.

F. Quantization of time for a mass

According to the Heisenberg uncertainty, there must be a non-zero minimum for time uncertainty for a mass object. This can be understood as time to have a “granularity”, raising the question how to interpret this in physical processes as such. If we assume, that any physical interaction of a mass with its environment requires time to

evolve, it can be hypothesized that the granularity of time be what has been applied in Eq. (7) already:

$$\sqrt{2} \sigma_{tU} \geq \frac{t_{pl}}{\alpha} = \frac{t_{pl} m_{pl}}{m} = \frac{\hbar}{mc_0^2} = \tau_{fluc} = \frac{\overline{\lambda}_c}{c_0}. \quad (44)$$

For example, for an electron this would result to a granularity in the range of 10^{-21} s, and for the smallest particle known so far, the Neutrino, it presumably could be in the range of $10^{-12} \dots 10^{-15}$ s.

For the minimum mass of an object required to exist in the Universe, as derived in Eq. (26), we gain:

$$\sqrt{2} \sigma_{tU} (m_{minU}) = \frac{\hbar}{\frac{\hbar}{R_U c_0} c_0^2} = \frac{R_U}{c_0} = 46.65 \text{ bn yrs}. \quad (45)$$

This appears to be logical in the sense that a mass in the Universe can only be noticed if it at least once in the time the Universe is existing¹⁰ would become part of any physical process.

G. Zero-gravitation and degree of quantization

Considering more compact potential wells than the Universe and with homogeneous mass density, there must be a limit where Gravon ground state energy level will become equal or higher than the depth of the respective gravitational potential well. This means that gravitation effect of a mass object ($m; r_m$) in a homogeneous mass density “cloud” ($M_C; R_C$) would vanish, if:

$$W_{Gr0} = \frac{\hbar c_0}{2R_C} \geq \frac{1}{2} \frac{mM_C G}{R_C} = \frac{1}{2} mc_0^2 \eta, \text{ with:} \\ \eta = \frac{R_U}{R_C} \frac{M_C}{M_U}. \quad (46)$$

While η is a scale factor to re-normalize zero-point energy of mass in the Universe towards the interaction of mass with the cloud. Reformulating the inequation yields:

$$mM_C \leq \frac{\hbar M_U}{c_0 R_U}, \text{ with:} \\ \sqrt{\frac{\hbar M_U}{c_0 R_U}} = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar c_0}{G}} = 2.176 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ kg} = m_{pl}. \quad (47)$$

This means, for an object with the product of its mass and cloud's mass being less than the square of the Planck-mass,

¹⁰Obviously, this is not the age of the Universe since it has expanded from presumed big bang and $R_U > R_H$ today. However, the argument for a mass to become part of a physical process at least once needs to apply to entire Universe.

the gravitation effect must be expected to vanish.

A different setup with hyperbolic potential arises for two mass objects $(m; r_m)$ and $(M; R_M)$ interacting over a distance $d > r_m + R_M$. The non-relativistic gravitational Bohr model¹¹ from Eq. (18) at ground state ($n=1$) yields:

$$r_{gB} = \frac{\hbar^2}{m^2 MG} \equiv d, \text{ thus: } m^2 M = \frac{\hbar^2}{dG}. \quad (48)$$

From this, three cases do arise:

(a) Significant quantization effects should be observed, if distance of mass objects is in the range of the gravitational Bohr radius. For example, for a distance of $d=6cm$ between a mass of 1 gram and a neutron. Another example are two identical mass objects with $1.4 \cdot 10^{-19} kg$ at this distance.

(b) For a distance less than the gravitational Bohr radius gravitational force should vanish since energy cannot be decreased below ground state.

(c) For a distance significantly larger than gravitational Bohr radius, gravitation effect should approach a continuum, i.e., quantization cannot be resolved in observation anymore.

To conclude, zero-gravitation and quantization effects should be considered for formation processes between particles converging out of gas, dust, and micro particles, which is for further study¹².

H. Entropy in the Universe

As discussed in section III.C, the size parameters (R_U, M_U) of the Universe also relate to a low-density black hole. With this, a Bekenstein-Hawking-Entropy [27], [28] given by:

$$S_{bh} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\ln(2) k_B c_0^3 A_{bh}}{4\hbar G} \quad (49)$$

can be derived, while for the Universe the surface of the black hole is: $A_{bhU} = 4\pi R_U^2$. Using the minimum for a mass to exist in the Universe from Eq. (26), as well as Eq. (9) found for G and Eq. (22) for the Ghoton energy, entropy can be formulated as:

$$S_{bhU} = \frac{1}{2} \ln(2) \pi k_B \frac{M_U}{m_{minU}} = 3.52110^{100} \frac{J}{K}. \quad (50)$$

In this, maximum entropy [29] in the Universe appears based on the maximum number of possible states given by the ratio of total mass in the Universe and the minimum possible particle mass. Due to the Einstein equivalence principle this can also be expressed by the ratio of the DE and the minimum gravitational energy realized in the Ghoton quantum:

$$S_{bhU} = \frac{1}{2} \ln(2) \pi k_B \frac{DE}{W_{Gh}}, \text{ with:} \quad (51)$$

$$DE = M_U c_0^2 \text{ and } W_{Gh} = \frac{\hbar c_0}{R_U} = m_{minU} c_0^2.$$

For the temperature as a black body, a Hawking-radiation from the black hole was proposed in [28], with:

$$T_H = \frac{\hbar c_0^3}{8\pi G M k_B}. \quad (52)$$

Again, for the Universe with the formula for G and the Ghoton energy it is found that:

$$T_{HU} = \frac{W_{Gh}}{8\pi k_B}. \quad (53)$$

Hence the temperature of the black body radiation for the Universe shall be based on the Ghoton energy, which appears to be consistent with the entropy derived above.

With this, reconsidering black holes in general, gravitational quantum particles to be emitted from them can be assumed to have an energy of:

$$W_{Gh}(R_{bh}) = \frac{\hbar c_0}{R_{bh}}. \quad (54)$$

I. Quantum origin of gravitation and inertial Equivalence Principle

A generalized law for gravitational energy and acceleration for two mass objects m and M separated by a distance r in the Universe can be described in the case of continuum as:

¹¹To use the non-relativistic formulas, $(m M) < m_{pl}^2$ must apply, as in the three case examples here.

¹²Apart from this, objects will experience gravitation effects from all other objects in the Universe, also including the zero-point acceleration as described above.

$W_{\text{spot}}(m, M, r) = \frac{-mMG}{r} = -\eta mc_0^2$, with:

$$\eta = \frac{R_U}{r} \frac{M}{M_U}, \text{ since } G = \frac{R_U c_0^2}{M_U}. \quad (55)$$

With η being the scale factor to re-normalize respective confinement of mass objects and size of mass related to the properties of the Universe.

Now I consider the two mass objects as confining each other in the Universe and describe them in Heisenberg uncertainty relations used as equations, hence realizing minimum energy possible. With uncertainties as:

$$\sigma_x = \frac{r}{\sqrt{2}}, \text{ and } \sigma_p = \frac{p}{\sqrt{2}}, \text{ yields: } p = \frac{\hbar}{r}. \quad (56)$$

$$\sqrt{2} \sigma_W = -W_{\text{spot}} = W_{\text{kin}} = \eta mc_0^2 \text{ and } \sqrt{2} \sigma_t = \frac{\hbar}{\eta mc_0^2}. \quad (57)$$

With this we gain for the force and acceleration¹³ between the two mass objects:

$$\frac{\sigma_p}{\sigma_t} = F = ma = m \frac{\eta c_0^2}{r} = mc_0^2 \frac{R_U}{r^2} \frac{M}{M_U}. \quad (58)$$

The force is attractive since momentum p increases with decreasing distance r due to Heisenberg uncertainty relation in Eq. (56).

The perspective for gravitation is, that it seems to originate from an instability contained in the quantum mechanical uncertainty, maximizing confined momentum, and minimizing distance between mass objects.

It is based on inertia, explaining the equivalence principle of inertial and gravitational acceleration. Hence, we find no such specific property like a „gravitational acceleration“ being different from inertia.

¹³For an object on the surface of the Earth for example the expected acceleration value is gained:

$$a_E = \frac{\eta_E c_0^2}{R_E} = c_0^2 \frac{R_U}{R_E} \frac{M_E}{M_U} = \left(2.998 \cdot 10^8 \frac{m}{s} \right)^2 \frac{4.413 \cdot 10^{26} m \cdot 5.972 \cdot 10^{24} kg}{(6.366 \cdot 10^6 m)^2 \cdot 5.943 \cdot 10^{53} kg} = 9.835 \frac{m}{s^2}.$$

¹⁴ For an average nucleon in the atomic nucleus arithmetic mean values of proton and neutron mass and radius are taken: $m_N = 1837m_e$ and $r_N = 1.122 fm$ (see Eq. (66) in subsection below). Note that in standard literature values in the range of $r_N = 0.9...1.4 fm$ are given, mainly depending on the number of nucleons in the atomic nucleus and constellations analyzed [30], [31], [32].

J. Quantum confinement in atomic nuclei

1. Potential energy in the atomic nucleus

Revisiting section III.G and Eq. (46), a further specific case with $W_{Gr0} = \frac{\hbar c_0}{2R} \gg \frac{1}{2} \frac{mMG}{R} = \frac{1}{2} mc_0^2 \eta$, meaning that required quantum mechanical zero-point energy in confinement being by far larger than the depth of the related gravitational potential, shall be analyzed.

In this context, I want to consider the basic principles of the atomic nucleus and the fundamental strong interaction force effect between nucleons.

Based on Eq. (29) the kinetic Gravon energy – i.e., the negative gravitational potential energy - for an average nucleon¹⁴ seen as confined in the potential well of the atomic nucleus with radius R_A and a homogenous mass distribution is:

$$W_{GrN} = W_{kinN} = -W_{\text{spot}N} = W_{0N} \left[\frac{3\eta_A}{2} - \frac{n_{Gr}^2}{2} \left(\frac{W_{Gh}(R_A)}{W_{0N}} \right)^2 \right],$$

with: $\eta_A = \frac{R_U}{R_A} \frac{M_A}{M_U}$, and: $R_A = r_N N_N^{\frac{1}{3}}$, $M_A = m_N N_N$,

$$W_{0N} = m_N c_0^2 = 938.9 MeV, \text{ and: } r_N = 1.122 fm. \quad (59)$$

The Gravon quantum number n_{Gr} will depend on the number of nucleons, while the law is different from the atomic shell model for electrons due to further effects to be considered in the atomic nucleus [30]. However, it can

be shown to approximately follow $n_{Gr} \sim \left(\frac{N_N}{g_s} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}}$, with

$g_s = 2$ due to the isospin degeneracy of the deuteron, i.e., of the proton-neutron pairs in the atomic nucleus. Hence Gravon energy in Eq. (59) does almost not dependent on the number of nucleons N_N . While the first term with re-normalization factor η is neglectable due tininess of atomic nuclei mass as compared to the mass of the Universe, from simplifying it results:

$$W_{kinN} = -\frac{1}{2g_s^{\frac{2}{3}}} \frac{[W_{Gh}(r_N)]^2}{W_{0N}} = -10.38MeV = -W_{BN}. \quad (60)$$

This means, an average negative kinetic energy - i.e., binding energy W_{BN} - will be required to realize the confinement.

Comparing this result to the established empirical Bethe-Weizsäcker (BW) droplet model [30], but for the volume and surface energy terms only - since Coulomb, asymmetry and pairing potential are not considered in the Graviton energy - the binding energy is found to be in the correct range, e.g.: $W_{BW} = 9.31...11.42MeV$ for

$$N_N = 20...70, \quad \text{since } W_{BW} = a_V + N_N^{\frac{1}{3}} a_S, \quad \text{with } a_V = 15.5MeV \text{ and } a_S = -16.8MeV.$$

Looking at the Thomas-Fermi model for the Fermi energy in the potential of the atomic nucleus, it is [31],[32]:

$$W_{FA} = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m_N r_N^2} \left(\frac{9\pi}{4g_s} \right)^{\frac{2}{3}} = \frac{(W_{Gh}(r_N))^2}{2W_{0N}} \left(\frac{9\pi}{4g_s} \right)^{\frac{2}{3}} \quad (61)$$

Yielding $W_{FA} = 60.67MeV$ without ($g_s = 1$) [32] and $W_{FA} = 38.22MeV$ with consideration ($g_s = 2$) [31] of isospin degeneration of nucleons, respectively.

Hence, in this work the Thomas-Fermi model is found to be directly based on the ratio of squared Ghoton energy and rest energy of the nucleon.

2. Binding energy from nucleon mass defect

Reflecting on the special situation, that the potential of the atomic nucleus and the strong interaction force between nucleons go hand in hand with a mass defect, the insights from the subsection above can serve as explanation. It appears to be that to realize the confinement in an atomic nucleus, a mass defect to deliver the missing kinetic energy must occur to the nucleons due to the laws of quantum mechanics, that otherwise would be violated. Setting up the expression for the mass defect:

$$\Delta m_N = \frac{W_{BN}}{c_0^2} = -\frac{W_{kinN}}{c_0^2} = -\frac{1}{2g_s^{\frac{2}{3}}} \frac{\hbar^2}{r_N^2 m_N c_0^2}, \quad (62)$$

this can be shown by reformulation into a Heisenberg minimum uncertainty $\sigma_p \sigma_x = \frac{\hbar}{2}$ required, with:

$$\sigma_p = \sqrt{\frac{\Delta m_N m_N}{2}} c_0 \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_x = r_N, \quad \text{or:} \quad (63)$$

$$\sigma_W = \frac{\sigma_p^2}{2m_N} = \frac{\Delta m_N c_0^2}{4} \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_t = \frac{\hbar}{2\sigma_W} = 1.27 \cdot 10^{-22} s \quad (64)$$

Furthermore, there must be limit for the mass defect, if a nucleon would be forced to the bottom of the potential well in the atomic nucleus, i.e., assuming a binding energy equal to the Fermi energy according to Eq. (61). This would lead to a minimum possible radius for the nucleon and distance between nucleons of:

$$r_{Nmin} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2g_s^{\frac{2}{3}}} \frac{\hbar^2}{m_N W_{FA}}} = r_N \left(\frac{9\pi}{4} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} = 0.585 fm. \quad \text{This is}$$

comparable with the range found in [30],[31],[32] for the point where the strong interaction force changes from being attractive to become repulsive.

3. Identity of Pion and Ghoton

In the year 1934 H. Yukawa predicted the existence of a quantum exchange particle - called Meson and later named Pion - to cause the strong interaction force effect within the deuteron, i.e., between the neutron and the proton as the key building block of the atomic nuclei [33].

The Pion was confirmed by detection in the Earth's atmosphere in 1946 [34], and Pion energy according to latest measurements as of the year 2020 taken from [35] is: $W_{\pi^\pm} = 139.57MeV$.

With this work, the value of the Pion energy is now found from an analytical approach to be identical to the Ghoton energy - which is the quantum gravitation exchange particle - of the potential well for the neutron and the proton confined within the volumetric radius of the deuteron R_{AD} :

$$W_{Gh}(R_{AD}) = \frac{\hbar c_0}{R_{AD}} = 139.56MeV, \quad \text{with: } R_{AD} = r_{ND} 2^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (65)$$

In this the radius of the nucleons in the deuteron r_{ND} is made up by the average value of half of the deuteron $r_d = 2.12562 fm$, to the degree as determined according to [36], and the sum of the root-mean-square electric charge radius of the proton $r_{pE} = 0.8409 fm$ and the root-mean-square charge radius of the neutron $r_n = 0.341 fm$, both taken from [35]:

$$r_{ND} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{r_d}{2} + (r_{pE} + r_n) \right) = 1.122 fm. \quad (66)$$

This average can be understood as effective radius for a nucleon in the deuteron under the permanent exchange of

Pions between the proton and the neutron, that make up the strong interaction force effect.

To summarize, the strong interaction force between nucleons in atomic nuclei can be derived and described analytically as a special case out of the quantum gravity model EQGM.

In this the potential well for the Ghoton is made up by the deuteron, and it is found that the Ghoton exhibits identical energy as the Pion, within the range of currently available precision in determination of the radius for the deuteron.

In addition, for the atomic nucleus, the Graviton energy of the nucleons, i.e., their gravitational kinetic energy, is found to be equivalent to nucleon binding energies empirically found for the strong interaction force effect.

K. Summary of gravitational energy interpretations

Along the different appearances of energies related to gravity used in the EQGM, it was found that there is an identity of the energies attached to mass in the Universe:

$$\begin{aligned} -W_{pot}(m) &= W_{kin}(m) = mc_0^2 = \sqrt{2} \sigma_{WU} \\ &= m\gamma\sigma_a \sqrt{2} R_U = \sigma_m \sqrt{2} \gamma g_{zp} R_U. \text{ With:} \end{aligned}$$

Newton gravitational potential energy, as negative identity for the gravitational kinetic energy of the mass related to $r = R_U$ at the boarder of the Universe.

Rest energy of mass according to Einstein's Equivalence Principle, which led to use of mass and energy synonymous in the General Relativity Theory in the Energy-Momentum Tensor [3].

Quantum mechanical uncertainty zero-point energy for mass, as shown in this work. This energy can be interpreted as fluctuations on a time scale τ_{fluc} in two ways:

1. As a so called "Zitterbewegung", a phenomenon first described in [37] for electrons. In EQGM it is found to cause zero-point acceleration for mass objects appearing as gravitational acceleration g_{zp} and being interpreted as kinetic energy fluctuations, with $\gamma=2$:

$$\sigma_{WU} \sqrt{2} := W_{kin} = mc_0^2.$$

2. As "mass-defect energy fluctuation", where zero-point energy is temporarily created out of mass and vice versa:

$$\sigma_{WU} \sqrt{2} := W_0 = mc_0^2.$$

Both interpretations, the Zitterbewegung and the mass

defect energy fluctuation, can also go hand in hand as a kind of duality in terms of a zigzag picture for fermions with rest mass m being a coupling parameter between two wave-functions propagating with the speed of light, as described in [6]. Based on the fluctuation time their minimum spatial expanse would be the reduced Compton wavelength (see Eq. (44)), aka the relativistic gravitational Bohr radius (see Eq (21)).

To summarize, the physical parameters of mass, rest energy of mass, negative gravitational potential and attached Newtonian zero-point kinetic energy, as well as quantum zero-point energy are found to be equivalent representations to characterize gravitation in the Universe. Moreover, the zero-point kinetic energy of a mass object in the Universe is found to appear on-top of the rest energy and being invariant regarding total mass and radius of the Universe.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The relatively simple EQGM looking at the Universe as composed of quantum wells delivers qualitative and quantitative explanation approaches for effects associated with DM and DE, and even an analytical approach to nuclear physics in line with observations.

It is found that gravity can be described as a quantum mechanical effect as such.

Furthermore, the quantum mechanical model as derived here can also serve to unify the description of fundamental forces for gravitation in the Universe and for the strong interaction force effect on nucleons in atomic nuclei.

The total on top energy appearing in the EQGM for the Universe is: $W_{Uzp} = M_U c_0^2 = DE = DM c_0^2 = 5.341 10^{70} J$.

The mass equivalent associated with this DE is the mass of the Universe M_U itself, which thus is also acting as DM. Hence, a DM as a kind of so far unknown mass is not required here since the gravitational zero-point acceleration has been identified to explain the effect of observed galaxy rotation violation.

Bekenstein-Hawking entropy of the Universe is conclusively found to be based on the ratio of DE versus Ghoton energy, equivalent to total mass of the Universe versus minimum possible mass of a particle in the Universe, respectively.

For the gravitational quantum effects that should exhibit discrete effects as discussed above, further study is required to design analyses and experiments for validation.

Finally, the Pion energy describing the strong interaction force effect in the deuteron is found to be identical to the energy of the Ghoton for the deuteron describing the

gravitational force.

Given the vast diversity and history of research in the field of quantum gravity done in the last decades, it must be beyond the scope of this work to discuss and assess the EQGM as compared to the variety of approaches.

Moreover, it is left for further study how the EQGM and its findings can also help to understand the evolution of the Universe and the atomic nuclei even better, from the origin and towards destination.

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VI. APPENDIX

APPENDIX A. RELATIVISTIC HEISENBERG UNCERTAINTY RELATION

The Heisenberg uncertainty relation shall be described for an inertial system of the Universe (U), with the mass moving with velocity v in it, and in the inertial system of the mass object itself (mo), where the mass is at rest. The Lorentz factor is described as: $\gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c_0^2}}}$. To generalize,

I do not exclude any of the physical parameters from uncertainty and hence do allow variances for all of them, leading to a generic form:

$$\sigma_m \sigma_a \sigma_t \sigma_x \geq \frac{\hbar}{2}. \quad (\text{A1})$$

To recapitulate, the following rules from Special Relativity Theory apply for two inertial systems moving with relative velocity v to each other [38]:

Relativistic increase of inertia increases momentum and energy of the mass object observed in the inertial system of the Universe, as described by the Lorentz factor.

Time scales of the observed other inertial system appear slower, i.e. decreased (time dilation).

Length scales of the observed other inertial system appear reduced (length contraction).

Time and length scales observed within each inertial system appear unchanged, thus also velocity and acceleration within each inertial system appear unchanged.

Hence the relative velocities of inertial systems to each other are observed at the same value in both systems.

The Heisenberg uncertainty applies within both inertial systems as:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{pU} \sigma_{xU} &\geq \frac{\hbar}{2}, \text{ and } \sigma_{WU} \sigma_{tU} \geq \frac{\hbar}{2}, \text{ and:} \\ \sigma_{pmo} \sigma_{xmo} &\geq \frac{\hbar}{2}, \text{ and } \sigma_{Wmo} \sigma_{tmo} \geq \frac{\hbar}{2}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A2})$$

The actual physical parameter and its variance are related so that Heisenberg uncertainty set as equation matches the ground state $n = 1$ of Bohr's postulate:

$$pr \equiv \hbar n, \text{ equals: } \sigma_p \sigma_x = \frac{\hbar}{2}, \text{ hence:}$$

$$\sigma_p = \frac{p}{\sqrt{2}}, \text{ and } \sigma_x = \frac{x}{\sqrt{2}}, \text{ with } x = r \quad (\text{A3})$$

Consequently, for energy and time uncertainty it is:

$$\sigma_W = \frac{W}{\sqrt{2}}, \text{ and } \sigma_t = \frac{t}{\sqrt{2}}. \quad (\text{A4})$$

Thus, for the inertial system of the Universe the momentum, the effective inertia and kinetic energy of the mass object resting in its inertial system (mo) must be adapted by the Lorentz factor. The uncertainty of energy can be rooted in the rest energy or in the kinetic energy:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{pU} &= \sigma_{mU} \sigma_{aU} \sigma_{tU} = \frac{p_U}{\sqrt{2}}, \text{ and} \\ \sigma_{WU} &= \sigma_{mU} \sigma_{aU} \sigma_{xU} = \frac{W_0}{\sqrt{2}} \quad \text{or} \quad = \frac{W_{kin}}{\sqrt{2}}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A5})$$

For the energy and momentum, the relativistic relations must be taken, note that relativistic energy contains the rest energy, while momentum is zero at rest:

$$\begin{aligned} W_U &= m_U c_0^2 = m_{mo} \gamma c_0^2 = W_0 + W_{kinU} \\ &= m_{mo} c_0^2 + m_{mo} (\gamma - 1) c_0^2, \text{ with: } m_{mo} = m. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A6})$$

$$p_U = \sqrt{\left(\frac{W_U}{c_0}\right)^2 - (m_U c_0)^2} = m_{mo} \gamma v_U = m_U a_U t_U. \quad (\text{A7})$$

For the inertial system of the mass object (mo) the time and length scale of the Universe must be adapted by the Lorentz factor:

$$\sigma_{pmo} = \sigma_{mmo} \sigma_{amo} \sigma_{tmo}, \text{ and: } \sigma_{xmo} = \sigma_{xU} \gamma^{-1}. \quad (\text{A8})$$

$$\sigma_{Wmo} = \sigma_{mmo} \sigma_{amo} \sigma_{xmo}, \text{ and: } \sigma_{imo} = \sigma_{tU} \gamma. \quad (\text{A9})$$

APPENDIX B. EXPANSION BASED ON FRIEDMAN EQUATION

I set up the Friedman equation [39] for a flat Universe according to the Standard Model of Cosmology (Λ -Cold Dark Matter-CDM), while considering the on-top gravitational zero-point acceleration as derived in the EQGM. Hence mass density ρ_U and the expansive pressure P_{exp} are assumed as:

$$\rho_U(r) = \frac{M_U}{(4/3)\pi r^3} \text{ and: } P_{exp}(r) = \frac{-W_{zpU}}{(4/3)\pi r^3},$$

while: $W_{zpU} = M_U c_0^2$. (B1)

With $a(r)$ being the scale factor for the radius of the Universe and $a = 1$ for the current state: $a(r) = \frac{r}{R_U}$. The Friedman equation with \ddot{a} being the second derivative for the scale factor $a(r)$ with respect to time, this means normalized acceleration can be written as:

$$\ddot{a}(r) = a(r) \left[\frac{-4\pi G}{3} \left(\rho_U(r) + \frac{3P_{exp}(r)}{c_0^2} \right) \right] - \frac{g_{zp}}{R_U} = \frac{3c_0^2}{2R_U^2},$$

$$\text{thus: } \ddot{a}(R_U) = 6.92110^{-37} s^{-2}. \quad (\text{B2})$$

Delivering the first derivative of the Hubble parameter with respect to time at $r=R_U$, i.e., for the scale parameter at $a=1$ yields:

$$\dot{H}_0 = \frac{\ddot{a}(R_U)}{a} - H_0^2, \text{ hence: } \dot{H}_0 = -3.92410^{-36} s^{-2}. \quad (\text{B3})$$

APPENDIX C. QUANTUM GRAVITATIONAL COUPLING PARAMETER

To describe the coupling between an object in a gravitation potential and its quantum particles, a gravitational coupling constant shall be derived analogous to the Sommerfeld fine-structure constant for electrodynamics [40].

The Sommerfeld fine-structure constant¹⁵ α_C is based on the Bohr atom model. It relates the velocity of the electron on its trajectory in a hydrogen atom in ground state $n = 1$ to the speed of light. Hence it serves for example to

describe emission- and absorption rates of photons from the electron. With the Bohr radius from Eq. (15) the electron velocity is: $v_{eB} = \frac{h}{2\pi r_B m_e} = \frac{q^2}{2\varepsilon_0 h}$, and hence:

$$\alpha_C = \frac{v_{eB}}{c_0} = 7.29210^{-3}. \quad (\text{C1})$$

Analogous to the derivation as for the electrodynamic case in the Bohr atom model, a gravitational coupling parameter is obtained. For the gravitational zero-point level a relativistic approach is needed here: $W_{zp} = W_{kin} = m\gamma c_0^2$, with $\gamma = 2$, this yields: $v = \sqrt{3}/2c_0$, hence the minimum gravitational coupling parameter is:

$$\alpha_{Gzp} = \frac{\sqrt{(3)}}{2} = 0.866. \quad (\text{C2})$$

Within the Universe α_{Gzp} will be running, i.e., increase further towards up to the value of one, if mass objects approach speed of light. Hence strong emission- and absorption interaction of Ghotons with mass objects in the Universe can be expected.

VII. REFERENCES

- [1] I. Newton, *Philosophiae Naturalis Principia Mathematica*. July 5, 1686, London, England
- [2] H. Cavendish, *Experiments to determine the density of the Earth*. June 21, 1798, Royal Society of England
- [3] A. Einstein, *Zur allgemeinen Relativitätstheorie*. 11. Nov 1915, Berlin, Germany
- [4] Q. Li, *et al.*, Measurements of the gravitational constant using two independent methods. *Nature*, 29. August 2018
- [5] H. Nicolai, *Quantum Gravity: The view from particle physics*, Jan 23, 2013, arXiv: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1301.5481v1>
- [6] R. Penrose, *The Road to Reality - A complete Guide to the Laws of the Universe*. (Random House, Inc.), 1st Ed., 2005, New York, USA, ISBN 978-0-679-77631-4
- [7] C. Kiefer, *Quantum Gravity*. (Oxford University Press), 3rd Edition, 2012, ISBN 978-01999585205
- [8] F. Zwicky, *On the Masses of Nebulae and of Clusters of Nebulae*, *Astrophys. J.* **86**, 1937
- [9] M. Milgrom, *MOND vs. dark matter in the light of historical parallels*. Elsevier *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part B*, **71**, Aug 2020
- [10] A. Riess *et al.*, *Observational Evidence from*

¹⁵With subscript C used here to denote that this coupling constant is related to Coulomb potential.

Supernovae for an Accelerating Universe and a Cosmological Constant. *Astron. J.* **116**, Sep 1998

[11] N. Aghanim *et al.*, Planck 2018 Results, VI, Cosmological parameters. *Astron. Astrophys – Special Issue* 641, A6, Mar 20, 2020

[12] S. Hossenfelder, T. Zingg, Analogue Gravity Models From Conformal Rescaling. Mar 17, 2020, arXiv: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1703.04462>

[13] W. Heisenberg, Über den anschaulichen Inhalt der quantentheoretischen Kinematik und Mechanik. *Z Phys*, **43**, 1927

[14] J. R. Gott III *et al.*, A Map of the Universe, *Astrophys J*, **624**, No. 2, 2005, <https://doi.org/10.1086/428890>

[15] J. D. Bekenstein, The modified Newtonian dynamics – MOND and its implications for new physics. Mar 27, 2007, arXiv: <https://arxiv.org/abs/astro-ph/0701848>

[16] M. Planck, Über irreversible Strahlungsvorgänge. §26, *Berichte der Königlich Preußischen Akademie der Wissenschaften*, Band 5, 1899, Berlin, Germany

[17] V. Faraoni, Three new roads to the Planck scale. May 27, 2017, arXiv: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1705.09749>

[18] N. Bohr, On the constitution of atoms and molecules. *Philosophical Mag. Series 6*, 26:151, Jul 1913

[19] C. Kittel, *Introduction to Solid State Physics*. 9th Edition, (John Wiley & Sons), Jul 2018, ISBN 978-1-119-45416-8

[20] S. Chandrasekhar, The Maximum Mass of Ideal White Dwarfs. *Astrophys J*, **74**, 1931, <https://doi.org/10.1086/143324>

[21] S. Weinberg, Universal Neutrino Degeneracy, 1962, *Phys. Rev.* **128**, Nov 1, 1962, <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRev.128.1457>

[22] M. Kamionkowski, A. G. Riess, The Hubble Tension and Early Dark Energy. Nov 8, 2022, arXiv: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2211.04492>

[23] T. M. C. Abbott *et al.*, Dark Energy Survey Year 3 Results: Cosmological Constraints from Galaxy Clustering and Weak Lensing. Mar 21, 2022, arXiv: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2105.13549>

[24] B. McBryan, Living in a Low density Black Hole, Dec. 3, 2013, arXiv: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1312.0340>

[25] C. King, Dual-Time Supercausality. *Physics Essays*, June 1, 1989, <https://doi.org/10.4006/1.3035859>

[26] L. de Broglie, The wave nature of the electron. Nobel Lecture, Dec 12, 1929

[27] J. D. Bekenstein, Black Holes & Entropy. *Phys Rev D* **7**, No. 8, Apr 15, 1973

[28] S. Hawking, Particle Creation by Black Holes. *Commun Math Phys*, 1975

[29] J. D. Bekenstein, Universal upper bound on the entropy-to-energy ratio for bounded systems. *Phys Rev D* **23**, No. 2, Jan 15, 1981

[30] Th. Mayer-Kuckuk, *Kernphysik*, (Teubner Verlag), 7. Auflage, 2002, ISBN 978-3-519-13223-3

[31] B. Povh, K. Rith, *Teilchen und Kerne*, (Springer Verlag), 5. Auflage, 1999, ISBN 3-540-659928-5

[32] K. Bethge, *Kernphysik – Eine Einführung*, (Springer Verlag), 1996, ISBN 3-540-61236-X

[33] H. Yukawa, On the Interaction of Elementary Particles. I, Proceedings of the Physico-Mathematical Society of Japan. 3rd Series, 1935, Vol. 17; https://www.jstage.jst.go.jp/article/ppmsj1919/17/0/17_0_48/article/-char/en

[34] C. M. G. Lattes *et al.*, Processes involving charged mesons, *Nature* 159, 1947. <https://doi.org/10.1038/159694a0>

[35] P. A. Zyla *et al.*, (Particle Data Group), *Prog. Theor. Exp. Phys.* 2020, 083C01 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1093/ptep/ptaa104>

[36] O. J. Hernandez *et al.*, The deuteron-radius puzzle is alive: A new analysis of nuclear structure uncertainties, *Physics Letters B* 778, 2018

[37] G. Breit, An interpretation of Dirac's Theory of the Electron. *Proc Nat Acad Sci USA* **14**, No. 7, 1928, <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.14.7.553>

[38] L. D. Landau, E. M. Lifshitz, *Theoretische Physik kurzgefasst*, Akademie Verlag Berlin, 1973

[39] A. Friedman, Über die Krümmung des Raumes. *Z Phys* **10**, 1922

[40] A. Sommerfeld, Zur Quantentheorie der Spektrallinien. *Ann Phys* **4**, 1916